

Neo Vernacular Kitchen: A Sustainable and Adaptive Housing Module Integrating Parametric Simulations and Real-Scale Prototyping

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Abstract. The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) is a temporary housing prototype developed as part of WP4 of SPOKE 5 of the VITALITY project. It explores how vernacular architectural principles can be reinterpreted through digital modelling, environmental simulation and transdisciplinary design approaches to formulate a self-sufficient and climate-sensitive housing system. The project synthesises passive environmental strategies with computational tools to optimise both energy efficiency and indoor environmental quality. At the heart of the design is a variable thermal transmittance wall, designed to modulate heat exchange in response to external climatic conditions, and a home garden that facilitates on-site food production and enhances ecological resilience.

The architectural layout prefabricated cross-laminated timber (CLT) structure and use of bio-based materials contribute to the creation of an environmentally sustainable and contextually adaptable housing model. The research uses a dual methodological framework: predictive simulations using Ladybug/Honeybee and EnergyPlus guide the iterative development of the design, while empirical data collected through a full-scale prototype provides real-world validation. A digital twin, continuously updated by real-time sensor feedback, enables behavioural optimisation, predictive maintenance and dynamic recalibration of the system. NVK seeks to challenge conventional, static and resource-intensive building paradigms. It proposes a responsive architectural system capable of adapting to both user interaction and environmental variability. Its design also allows NVK to be considered both as a stand-alone emergency shelter module and as a comfort-generating living module within a housing complex.

By integrating traditional architectural intelligence with advanced simulation workflows and continuous in-situ monitoring, NVK offers a methodological framework that combines digital technologies and ecological adaptability.

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1 Introduction

In architecture, the term “vernacular” describes building practices shaped by local environmental, cultural, and material conditions, developed over time through collective knowledge rather than codified design [1]. As demonstrated in studies such as [2], vernacular typologies—particularly in Mediterranean and arid climates—exhibit high thermal performance, largely due to passive design strategies like thermal mass and natural ventilation. The main strategies observed in Mediterranean vernacular architecture [3] include compact urban and rural layouts, thick masonry walls, optimal orientation of building volumes and openings, spatial organization around internal courtyards, the use of semi-open spaces, external shutters, lightweight shading devices such as pergolas, and integrated vegetation. Research conducted on traditional Cypriot architecture highlights its capacity to adapt to diverse climatic zones across the island. A fundamental feature is the use of local materials with high thermal mass, which contributes to passive thermal regulation. As demonstrated in southern Italy, the thermal inertia of the envelope plays a key role in maintaining stable indoor temperatures, allowing adequate comfort with minimal energy input during colder periods [4].

The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK), developed within WP4 of SPOKE 5 of the VITALITY project,—specifically within Spoke 5, “Environmental, Economic, and Social Sustainability of Living and Working Environments”—and developed as part of Output 4.1 “Innovative Design Methods for Eco-Sustainability of Products for the Living Environments”, reinterprets these principles through computational modelling, environmental simulation, and transdisciplinary design [5]. It investigates how architectural knowledge embedded in traditional forms can inform low-energy, self-sufficient living systems responsive to climate variability [2], [3].

The main features of the project include a variable thermal transmittance wall (VTTW), which can influence the thermal stability of the external wall instead of traditional masonry, and a home cultivator (HC), which promotes on-site food production and circular metabolic flows. The prefabricated CLT structure and the integration of natural materials improve the sustainability and replicability of the prototype.

The research employs a dual methodology: predictive simulations using tools such as Ladybug, Honeybee, and EnergyPlus guide early-stage design, while a full-scale prototype allows for in-situ testing. A continuously updated digital twin, fed by real-time environmental and behavioural data, enables adaptive calibration, predictive maintenance, and user-involved control [6].

NVK challenges conventional static housing models by proposing a performative architecture that evolves through user interaction and environmental feedback. It aligns with contemporary posthumanist theories, such as Harman and Morton’s concept of hyperobjects and Object-Oriented Ontology (OOO), which frame buildings and their components as active agents in ecological systems [7], [8]. By merging vernacular intelligence, ecological sensitivity, and digital innovation, NVK establishes a methodological framework for a dynamic and context-aware architecture, where sustainability is treated not as a fixed metric, but as a continuously negotiated performance.

2 Digital & Green Transition in Contemporary Architecture

The accelerating shift towards sustainable and high-performance buildings has prompted architectural research to embrace a more holistic paradigm—one that synthesises vernacular intelligence with digital innovation. The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) is situated within this evolving framework, proposing a housing model that reinterprets traditional construction principles through computational methodologies, thus enabling a form of architecture that is both culturally grounded and technologically responsive [9].

The NVK investigates how vernacular passive environmental strategies—derived from local climatic, material, and cultural contexts—can be systematically re-integrated into contemporary zero-energy architectural frameworks. Moving beyond the replication of historical aesthetics, the research isolates the performative logic of traditional typologies, emphasizing the functional value of thermal inertia, optimal solar orientation, and passive ventilation systems. These strategies, historically refined through empirical adaptation, are reframed as foundational principles for regenerative and resource-efficient design, aligning with Banham’s interpretation of pre-industrial architecture as environmentally attuned systems. [10] [11].

The Mediterranean trullo is a paradigmatic example. With its thick dry-stone walls, vaulted conical roof and strategically placed openings, the trullo embodies a passive climate control strategy that has endured over time. Numerical simulations without HVAC systems show that the Trullo maintains comfortable internal conditions in summer without mechanical cooling, thanks to its thermal mass and natural ventilation linked to the shape of the structure [12]. The aim is to reproduce an innovative spatial device that can offer the same thermal stability, using the wooden mass of CLT (Cross Laminated Timber) combined with a responsive and dynamic plant support system distributed throughout the wall and with low energy consumption. This reinterpretation is made possible by parametric tools and energy simulation software, which allow performance variables to be tested and optimised in a predictive manner]. This transition—from historically passive systems to intelligent, adaptive frameworks—demands a transdisciplinary research culture. In the NVK, traditional passive strategies are augmented through technological innovations such as the Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall, which modulates thermal behavior in real time. This component reflects a broader architectural shift from fixed energy-saving features to dynamic systems that respond to changing environmental inputs [13] [14].

The philosophical foundation of this approach is informed by Object-Oriented Ontology (OOO), which decentralises non-human actors—materials, systems, environments—as co-agents in architectural performance [7]. Morton’s notion of extends this understanding, portraying systems such as climate as temporally and spatially distributed entities beyond full human apprehension [8] [15]. Within this ontological framework, the NVK emerges not as an object in space, but as a relational and performative interface.

In rejecting formal mimicry and embracing operative principles, the NVK exemplifies how traditional knowledge can be retranslated through computational processes. Real-time simulation, bio-integrated systems, and data-informed adaptability converge to form a design model in which sustainability is not a static attribute but a condition in

flux—shaped by feedback, transformation, and interdependence among human and non-human agents. This dynamic understanding of performance challenges conventional sustainability metrics, proposing instead a system that evolves in dialogue with its users and its environment.

3 The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen System: Structure and Components

3.1 Beyond Disciplines: The Transdisciplinary Synthesis of NVK

The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) emerges as the outcome of a transdisciplinary design process that integrates expertise from architecture, engineering, agronomy, and computational design. Developed within WP4 of Spoke 5 of the VITALITY project, the NVK is not merely a building prototype but a systemic architectural organism in which material, technological, and ecological components operate in synergy.

The collaboration between institutions has played a critical role in shaping the NVK's architecture. The University of Camerino contributed to the development of the technological and environmental design approach, while digital modelling and simulation systems were supported by its Department of Computer Science. The Polytechnic University of Marche was instrumental in developing parametric tools and sustainable product design methods, particularly in integrating industrial design methodologies with environmental control strategies. The Home Cultivator System (HCS)—a defining element of NVK—was developed in conjunction with agronomic specialists, facilitating the integration of vertical indoor agriculture into the architectural envelope. The University of Perugia contributed key innovations in the design of the Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall, a system that bridges passive thermoregulation strategies and real-time climate responsiveness.

In this sense, NVK is not merely a housing prototype but a systemic integration of material, digital, and ecological processes. Each component—from construction materials to interactive environmental controls—functions as part of a holistic architectural organism. This systematisation of good practices allows researchers to quantify and validate both the isolated performance of each subsystem and the overall contribution of NVK as an integrated, self-sufficient entity. While this integrated perspective enhances the capacity to address complex environmental and spatial challenges, transdisciplinary approaches remain the subject of ongoing debate. They are often contested and not yet fully embedded in mainstream research and practice, despite being increasingly recognized as essential tools for interpreting and engaging with the shifting ontologies of contemporary ecological phenomena [16] [17].

3.2 Structure and Architectural Envelope

The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) presents a compact and highly integrated spatial layout, occupying a square footprint of 3.9 x 3.9 meters and reaching a total height of 4.50 meters. The volumetric configuration is defined by a truncated pyramidal roof,

which begins at 2.10 meters and culminates in a central clerestory skylight, enhancing both natural ventilation and zenithal illumination (see Fig.1). This geometry, inspired by traditional rural annexes and trulli, reinforces a context-sensitive yet simplified architectural language.

Fig. 1. NVK plans: roof plan (left), plan (center) and 3d view.

The internal environment combines cooking and living functions in a continuous, flexible space. The entire structure is elevated on a modular timber platform that rests on prefabricated footings, allowing for minimal site impact and integrating the technological systems below the floor level. The platform's aluminum substructure is clad in wooden decking panels, enhancing the project's commitment to sustainability and reversibility.

The primary load-bearing system consists of 12 cm cross-laminated timber (CLT) panels, prefabricated for efficient assembly. Approximately 56 m² of vertical surfaces and 15 m² of flooring are covered by these panels, ensuring structural stability and thermal mass. Externally, the envelope is insulated with 6 cm of expanded cork, a breathable, renewable material that supports both thermal inertia and acoustic performance. A three-coat lime-based plaster, applied over the insulation, ensures fire resistance and moisture control while evoking Mediterranean vernacular aesthetics with its warm reddish hue. Internally, lime-based plaster provides continuity, contributing to a healthy and breathable indoor environment.

A radiant heating system is embedded within the internal lime finish of the vertical walls, forming part of the Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall strategy. Polypropylene pipes extend over 135 linear meters across approximately 30 m² of surface, transforming the CLT panels into active thermal regulators by leveraging their mass to stabilize indoor temperatures efficiently.

The fenestration strategy prioritizes energy performance. A glazed entrance door (90 x 205 cm) ensures accessibility and daylight, while a large wooden-framed aperture accommodates the integrated home cultivator system—described in Section 3.4—which links food production with interior comfort and ecological design principles [19]. The clerestory skylight (90 x 90 cm), placed at the apex of the roof, directs natural light into the heart of the space, reinforcing both thermal gain and visual comfort.

Sectional drawings illustrate the building's material layering, from the prefabricated piers and raised platform to the insulated CLT walls and skylight. The total wall stratigraphy reaches 30 cm, evidencing the project's focus on performance and envelope optimization.

The elevations reveal a compact, monolithic volume where solid-to-void ratios favor enclosure and insulation. Openings are deliberately limited and strategically placed to preserve energy efficiency and formal clarity. The glazed main façade provides daylight and cross-ventilation, while the other façades remain largely opaque, punctuated only by shallow recesses that accentuate the building's visual simplicity and vernacular references.

3.3 Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall: An Adaptive System for Energy Comfort

The Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall system integrates a network of fluid-carrying pipes within standard wall constructions (horizontal, vertical, or oblique) of any material. A circulating heat transfer fluid, driven by a pump, facilitates heat exchange through the wall's thickness, enabling transfer from interior to exterior and vice versa. The system control relies on a differential temperature strategy: outdoor and indoor temperature sensors (T_i and T_e) guide pump activation (see Fig.2).

Fig. 2. The Variable Thermal Transmittance wall principle

During winter, effective wall insulation typically prevents operation. However, in transitional seasons, solar radiation can heat the exterior wall, allowing the fluid to efficiently transport this heat indoors. Conversely, during warm periods when outdoor temperatures fall below the indoor thermal comfort setpoint, especially at night, the system enhances heat dissipation from the interior to the exterior by reducing the wall's effective thermal resistance and thermal mass. The system incorporates a control unit that processes temperature data and manages pump operation. The pipe-embedding layers are built from high thermal conductivity materials (e.g., plasterboard, cement), while the core layers can be of any suitable material. Temperature sensors are strategically placed within the high-conductivity layers, avoiding thermal bridges and direct heat sources. The wall can be segmented into independently controlled fluid circuits. Pipes are typically made of plastic, copper, or iron, similar to radiant panel materials, and the

heat transfer fluid is water-based, potentially with glycol additives (10-40% concentration) for freeze protection, adjusted to the local climate [18].

3.4 Home Cultivator: From Traditional Windows to Integrated Biological Systems

Domestic vertical farming is a new frontier for urban agriculture. This technology that was built for space will likely be the home appliances of the kitchens of the future. The original idea, developed in the 90s by researchers from the North American Space Agency (NASA) to support long space missions and travels, has been translated first into a new industry with the appearance of the first plant factories in the 2010 [19], followed then by the “container farms”, and lately by relatively small size devices that could fit both in domestic environment and in the hospitality sector.

The basic principle of these devices is to cultivate plants in an indoor environment in stacked layers using artificial lights. In this fully controlled environment where water, light, nutrients, oxygen, and carbon dioxide are opportunely supplied, various vegetables could be grown. Leafy greens, aromatic plants, and edible flowers could be grown up to different stages ranging from seed sprouts and microgreens to baby leaves and full-grown crops.

Some of the most important and best features of these appliances can be summarized by the fact that these devices can produce high quality vegetables productions with characteristics of incommensurable freshness and taste and include high nutritive values as well. These products are real zero kilometers, since they are produced directly in the place of consumption. This could reduce the carbon footprint related to the transport of these vegetables; this impact nowadays could be very high if these products are coming out of season from the other hemisphere. It could be reduced also the food waste by reducing the large amount of food that becomes unsaleable before being on the shelf due to longer storage time and transport. These products are also considered real pesticide free, being grown in absence of any chemical treatments by choice thanks to the reduced risks of pathogens infections due to the protected environment.

Integrating these devices into the domestic environment can introduce an alternative agricultural production system able to contribute to food production in situations of climatic stress that could occur temporarily, or permanently such as in extreme environments. In this sense it could be only one of the potential solutions to cope with future food security challenges.

These appliances may have positive effects on both human wellbeing and on environmental health. They could introduce potentially relevant air quality improvements inside the domestic environment. This technology is seen as a water use efficient technology and could be considered also as a viable alternative to land consumption in certain densely urbanized areas.

However, it should be noted that these systems could have a significant impact on the carbon footprints due to high energy consumption, if not properly managed, and unless the required energy is mainly or entirely derived from renewable resources that possibly could be auto produced in the domestic environment.

New technologies and innovations have been integrated in this new generation of domestic appliances that could help in reducing some of the drawbacks of the actual

devices and that could promote both the rational use of scarce resources and a more sustainable circular economy.

These new devices proposed are challenging the way the indoor environment will be conceived and perceived in the next future and we think that the integration into the NVK could make an important contribution for many reasons, some of them already mentioned above.

4 Predictive Simulations in NVK Design

4.1 Objectives and evaluation criteria of the simulation process

The evaluation of the Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) relies on two complementary simulation environments, aimed at cross-verifying modeling approaches using data from the full-scale prototype [20]. The first environment, developed in Rhino/Grasshopper with Ladybug, Honeybee-Radiance, and Honeybee-Energy, enables detailed analysis of solar radiation, daylight, and passive gains through a parametric modeling approach. However, it lacks precision in simulating transient heat transfer and dynamic energy demand. The second environment, based on EnergyPlus and OpenStudio (integrated into SketchUp), offers deeper insights into internal gains, thermal mass, and ventilation through time-based simulation. A key feature of the NVK is the variable thermal transmittance wall, designed to dynamically respond to external climate conditions, optimizing heat flow for seasonal comfort and ensuring the thermal stability of the wall.

To enhance simulation reliability, a customized EPW weather file based on the "Representative Monthly Day" methodology was employed. These representative days condense monthly average climatic parameters (solar radiation, temperature, humidity, wind speed, etc.), reducing computational effort and supporting simplified design simulations [20]. Widely used in scientific contexts, representative days offer consistent performance results and are easier to construct than full climate datasets, making them suitable for iterative comparisons based on real conditions of a real day. Cross-validation between both environments ensures a more robust evaluation. Rhino/Grasshopper is most effective during early design exploration, while EnergyPlus provides deeper energy and comfort assessments. Empirical data from NVK's physical monitoring—operative temperatures, solar gains, and ventilation—will validate simulation outputs. This iterative feedback loop supports a performance-driven design approach where simulations inform construction choices [21][22].

4.2 Methodologies and Tools for Environmental Simulations: Environmental Simulation in Rhinoceros 7 with Ladybug and Honeybee.

The NVK CAD model was implemented in Rhinoceros 7, using Ladybug, Honeybee-Radiance, and Honeybee-Energy plug-ins. Simulations were fundamental in defining the thermal "core" of the structure, designed for stable interior comfort and potential emergency use.

Simulations employed the EPW climate file for San Benedetto del Tronto, limited to the 5:00–22:00 interval and analyzed for North and South orientations to reduce computation time. Ladybug tools calculated direct sunlight hours, incident radiation and irradiance, and shading effectiveness on building surfaces.

Honeybee refined the model, simulating indoor solar exposure, cumulative annual irradiance, and operative temperature distributions. A basic HVAC system was implemented to maintain interior temperatures between 13 °C and 21 °C. Material characterization—absent in Ladybug—was handled in Honeybee: transparent components featured $U = 1.5 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$, $\text{SHGC} = 0.5$, $\text{VT} = 0.6$; default software values were used for opaque elements.

Natural lighting was assessed using the “Daylight Autonomy” tool, and surface temperature distributions were visualized through “Color Faces” and “Color Rooms,” offering a comprehensive picture of the NVK’s thermal behavior

4.3 Energy Modelling and Dynamic Simulation Workflow in EnergyPlus.

Dynamic thermal simulations were conducted in EnergyPlus to assess NVK’s energy demand and comfort performance [20]. The geometry was modeled in SketchUp with OpenStudio, enabling the development of a multi-zone energy model aligned with the NVK’s internal layout. This was exported to EnergyPlus, where material properties (U -values, thermal mass, solar absorptance) were assigned for realistic heat transfer simulation. Simulations incorporated the representative day EPW file [21], capturing typical local conditions for San Benedetto del Tronto. Glazing properties and shading systems were included to evaluate solar gain, daylight, and adaptive fenestration strategies for comfort and energy efficiency. The building was modeled as a single thermal zone with internal loads (occupants, lighting, appliances), and airflow modeled based on permeability and wind exposure. Key outputs included operative temperatures, solar radiation, daylight availability, and natural ventilation effectiveness.

EnergyPlus supports a feedback-driven design process, where results guide material and technological decisions. Empirical data from the constructed prototype will further validate and refine the simulations. While computationally robust, model predictions may diverge from real-world performance due to construction-phase variabilities [22] [23]

5 From Virtual Model to Physical Prototype: Validation Through Digital Twin

The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) represents not only a digitally informed housing prototype but also a systemic model capable of adaptation, replication, and real-world application. As the project transitions from computational design to physical implementation, it initiates a critical validation phase through full-scale prototyping and empirical monitoring. The prototype, currently under preparation for construction at the University of Camerino’s San Benedetto del Tronto campus, will be installed in a site selected for its climatic diversity and contextual relevance. This testing ground provides an opportunity to assess the NVK’s capacity to perform under dynamic environmental conditions and to confirm the predictive accuracy of the simulations outlined in previous phases.

The construction process—based on prefabricated CLT panels, modular footings, and integrated passive-active systems—serves as a means of verifying the feasibility and replicability of the design logic. The prototype is conceived as both a demonstrative artefact and a functional living unit, intended to host a dense array of sensors and data collection systems.

These will record operative temperatures, solar exposure, humidity levels, and airflow patterns, offering a robust dataset for comparing projected and actual performance. The Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall will undergo thermal response assessment to verify its ability to regulate comfort through passive and semi-active modulation. Likewise, the integrated home cultivator system will be evaluated for its contribution to microclimatic regulation and food self-sufficiency, underlining the NVK's ambition to combine ecological intelligence with daily living.

A key feature of the validation strategy is the integration of a digital twin—an evolving virtual counterpart that mirrors the physical prototype by receiving continuous sensor input. This two-way interaction enables not only real-time behavioral analysis but also adaptive recalibration of system parameters. Through this feedback loop, the NVK becomes a dynamic, learning environment capable of predictive maintenance and energy optimization, aligning with emerging research in smart building analytics and high-resolution environmental monitoring [24]. Moreover, this approach facilitates long-term performance tracking, ensuring that the project remains responsive to both climatic and user-specific variables over time.

The digital twin architecture also plays a crucial role in enabling scalability. By capturing a range of environmental responses and occupant interactions, the system can inform site-specific variations of the NVK model. Parametric tools allow design elements—such as material layers, solar strategies, and energy systems—to be recalibrated based on diverse climatic inputs, enabling broader deployment scenarios from dense urban contexts to rural or off-grid environments. These adaptive potentials are closely tied to the concept of the Urban Digital Twin, which provides a framework for sustainable urban planning and multi-scalar design strategies [25] [26].

In this way, the NVK moves beyond its role as a one-off prototype. It becomes a methodological platform for architectural innovation—merging digital modelling, ecological awareness, and human-centered adaptability. By embedding transdisciplinary knowledge into a reproducible framework, the project offers a compelling model for future living systems that are responsive, data-informed, and environmentally grounded. This integrated approach challenges conventional architectural paradigms by positioning buildings not as fixed objects, but as interactive and evolving agents within a broader ecological and technological continuum.

6 Conclusions

The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) demonstrates the potential of integrating vernacular architectural intelligence with advanced computational tools to address pressing environmental, social, and technological challenges in contemporary housing. As a modular and adaptive prototype, the NVK exemplifies a systemic design approach grounded in transdisciplinary collaboration, bridging architecture, agronomy, environmental engineering, and digital simulation.

While performance results are still under development and empirical data from the physical prototype are currently being processed, this article primarily aimed to highlight an innovative transdisciplinary methodology for architectural experimentation in sustainable living systems. The methodological framework—based on predictive simulations, full-scale prototyping, and digital twin integration—offers a robust foundation for iterative design and future validation.

The incorporation of features such as the Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall and the Home Cultivator System shows how passive design strategies can be reinterpreted through digital workflows to enhance resilience, comfort, and sustainability. The NVK challenges static architectural paradigms by framing the building as an active agent within a broader ecological system. The implementation of a digital twin further strengthens this paradigm, enabling real-time monitoring, adaptive calibration, and predictive maintenance.

Ultimately, the NVK serves as a methodological platform for future research and design innovation, where tradition and technology converge to form responsive, data-informed, and ecologically attuned living systems. Its replicability and adaptability mark it as a forward-looking model within the evolving discourse of regenerative architecture and sustainable urban development.

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